

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SHERIFF****FIRST NAME: MOHAMED****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: QUIZ****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied U.S. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (Footnote).

The author used Zotero to insert references.

The author used Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access).

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 10%

The author used the following software (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10).

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the primary purpose of a thesis statement in a research paper?¹

- To summarize the entire paper
- To present the main argument or claim of the paper**
- To list all the sources used in the paper
- To provide background information on the topic

2. What is the purpose of an abstract in a research paper?²

- To provide a detailed explanation of the methodology
- To summarize the main points and findings of the paper**
- To list all the references used in the paper

¹ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth edition (Chicago London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 23–28.

² Ibid., 266 & 401.

- To introduce the background of the study
3. What is the main function of the methodology section in a research paper?³
- To discuss the results of the study
- To review the literature related to the study
- To describe the research methods and procedures used**
- To provide a summary of the findings
4. What is the primary focus of a dissertation concept paper?⁴
- To present the final findings of the research
- To outline the research problem and proposed methodology**
- To review the literature related to the research topic
- To provide a detailed budget for the research
5. Which of the following is a key component of quantitative research?⁵
- Thematic analysis
- Grounded theory
- Statistical analysis**
- Narrative inquiry

³ James Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Florida State University, 2017), 32–41.

⁴ Ibid., 2 & 6.

⁵ Ibid., 7, 10, 27.

6. What is the purpose of a literature review in a dissertation?⁶
- To present new experimental data
 - To summarize and synthesize existing research on the topic**
 - To outline the research methodology
 - To provide a detailed budget for the research
7. Which section of a dissertation typically includes the research questions and hypotheses?⁷
- Literature Review
 - Methodology
 - Introduction**
 - Results
8. What is the purpose of reflexivity in qualitative research?⁸
- To ensure the researcher's biases are minimized**
 - To increase the sample size
 - To enhance the statistical power of the study
 - To simplify the data collection process

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*, Fourth Edition (Thousand Oaks, Calif: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2019), 31–31.

⁷ Ibid., 74.

⁸ Ibid., 46–47.

9. Which chapter in a qualitative dissertation typically includes a detailed description of the research methodology?⁹
- Introduction
 - Literature Review
 - Methodology**
 - Conclusion
10. Which of the following is a common method of data collection in qualitative research?¹⁰
- Surveys
 - Experiments
 - Interviews**
 - Statistical analysis

⁹ Ibid., 251–56.

¹⁰ Ibid., 454–457.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*. Fourth Edition. Thousand Oaks, Calif: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2019.

Sampson, James. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition. Chicago London: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

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